

ISic1460

I.Sicily inscription 1460

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

sandstone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. οἴμοι ὄ ηύ

2. ψι

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 284892

EDR 112234

EDCS 41300081

EDCS 64800255

PHI 175695

Bibliography

Dubois, L. 1989. Inscriptions grecques dialectales de Sicile : contribution à

l'étude du vocabulaire grec colonial. Rome. At 66 (http://www.persee.fr/doc/efr_0000-0000_1989_cat_119_1)

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. *Sikelika* 6. Palermo. At 97

Arena, R. 1996. Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia. Iscrizioni di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.34

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1964-1965. intervento. *Kokalos*. 10-11: 481-484. At 481

Guarducci, M. 1967-1978. Epigrafia greca. Rome. At 320 no.11

Lejeune, M. 1970. Notes d'épigraphie sicilienne. *Kokalos*. 16: 16-29. At 18

Brugnone, A. 2006. Note epigrafiche selinuntine. *Thalassa*. 3: 45-123. At B6 tav.13.60

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